

OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN THE TRUCKING SERVICE BUSINESSES IN LUCENA CITY: A FOUNDATION FOR EFFECTIVE LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Aim: This study explores the intricate connections between operational efficiency and customer satisfaction in the logistics and transportation sectors of Lucena.

Methodology: The researcher collected direct responses from the participants using a descriptive design. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency distributions, percentages, and Pearson correlations, were used to analyze and interpret the data.

Results: The satisfaction assessment revealed positive evaluations across various dimensions, highlighting the significance of aesthetics, technological integration, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness. Furthermore, a strong positive correlation ($r = .755$, $p < .001$) is found, highlighting the connection between improved operational efficiency and higher levels of customer satisfaction.

Conclusion: This study concludes with practical recommendations for optimizing operational efficiency and improving customer satisfaction. These recommendations include strategies for facility maintenance, reliable delivery, staff training, and technology integration. It also suggests avenues for future research such as investigating the impact of emerging technologies and sustainability practices on operational efficiency.

Keywords: *Trucking Services, Operational Efficiency, Logistics Management, Lucena City*

INTRODUCTION

The US trucking industry is indispensable, as it transported 71.6% of goods valued at \$10.4 trillion in 2017. Essential for transporting 70% of all US freight, the transportation industry plays a vital role in numerous sectors, ensuring the delivery of everyday goods. Without it, critical industries would be impacted within 24 hours, which could have a significant effect on the nation. Employing around 800,000 truck drivers, the industry contributes to the health and strength of the economy. Launching a truck logistics business holds promise but requires dedication and hard work due to its crucial role in sustaining the US economy (ustKAL, June 28, 2019).

Zooming out to a broader perspective, the freight and logistics market in the Philippines is poised for significant growth. It is estimated to be worth \$18.03 billion in 2023, with projections indicating that it will reach \$25.38 billion by 2028, driven by a compelling compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7.08% during the forecast period. The ongoing pandemic has led to a surge in e-commerce activities within the country. This shift is driven by changes in consumer behavior, as an increasing number of people choose to shop online to minimize their potential exposure to health risks. This trend is expected to continue, especially because of the growing number of online retailers entering the market.

The demand for warehouse facilities in the Philippines remains robust, primarily fueled by the thriving e-commerce sector. This trend bodes well for the industrial and logistics real estate sector, which is projected to experience substantial growth in 2022. Projections point to increased activities in manufacturing, logistics, and e-commerce, further underlining the sector's importance. Furthermore, the industrial vacancy rate in the Cavite-Laguna-Batangas (CALABA) corridor has decreased due to rising demand for warehouse and storage space, particularly from fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) companies, reflecting the ongoing expansion of the online retail market.

The e-commerce sector is set to make a significant contribution to the country's economy, with an anticipated value of around PHP 1.2 trillion (USD 25 billion) by 2022, according to the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI)'s e-commerce roadmap. Additionally, the growing need for cold storage facilities is expected to boost demand for industrial assets in the coming 12 to 36 months. By 2023, the Board of Investments (BOI) foresees that the country's cold chain sector will generate PHP 20 billion (USD 417 million) in income.

This shift towards digital operations within the logistics sector is primarily led by major e-commerce players, including Lazada, Zalora, and Shopee, who collaborate with tech-driven logistics firms like Ninja Van and Lalamove. This digital transformation promises increased transparency in order tracking, reduced lead times, and expedited customs clearance processes, potentially reducing processing times to just 3-5 business days (Mordor Intelligence - Philippines Freight and Logistics Market).

A growing logistics and transportation industry is seen in Lucena City, a bustling industrial hub in the center of the Philippines, and it is vital to the local economy. The foundation of this region's

effective transportation of resources and goods, which promotes economic development, is provided by trucking service companies. Though the industry is significant, there are several obstacles that it must overcome to improve operational effectiveness and, by extension, the state of logistics management as a whole. Lucena City transportation service companies are the target of this study's efforts to increase operational effectiveness. Building a strong basis for effective logistics management in this dynamic environment is the primary goal.

Despite the undeniable economic importance of the trucking services industry in Lucena City, there exists a noticeable research gap. Limited in-depth studies have been conducted to comprehensively address the operational challenges and opportunities specific to this region. Issues such as traffic congestion, road conditions, regulatory hurdles, and the need for streamlined logistics processes pose substantial hurdles to operational efficiency. These problems not only affect the performance of individual businesses but also have broader implications for the regional economy. Moreover, in an era where logistics management is becoming increasingly sophisticated and technology-driven, the trucking services businesses in Lucena City must adapt and innovate to remain competitive. The absence of recent, data-driven research leaves local businesses and service providers without a well-informed foundation to optimize their operations, ultimately affecting the growth and competitiveness of Lucena City in the larger regional context.

The rationale for this research stems from the compelling need to address these challenges and provide a strong foundation for enhancing operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and logistics management in Lucena City's trucking service businesses. By shedding light on these operational issues and offering evidence-based solutions, this study aspires to make a meaningful contribution to both academic and practical domains. A comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by the industry, the identification of best practices for logistics management, and the enhancement of customer satisfaction can collectively bolster the competitiveness of Lucena City's businesses, attract further investment, and contribute to the overall economic development of the region. This research aligns with a broader vision of fostering a more efficient, sustainable, and economically vibrant Lucena City through improved logistics and trucking services.

Research Questions

This study addressed the following key questions:

1. How does operational efficiency influence Lucena City's trucking industry across the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of:
 - 1.1 Tangibles
 - 1.2 Reliability
 - 1.3 Responsiveness
 - 1.4 Assurance
 - 1.5 Empathy?
2. How do the respondents rate the level of satisfaction with the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, specifically in terms of:
 - 2.1 Tangibles
 - 2.2 Reliability
 - 2.3 Responsiveness
 - 2.4 Assurance
 - 2.5 Empathy

3. Is there a significant correlation between SERVQUAL dimensions and customer satisfaction in Lucena City's trucking sector?
4. How does operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking services support the foundation of effective logistics management?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The research on "Operational Efficiency in the Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City: A Foundation for Effective Logistics Management" is centered around Lucena City, a vibrant industrial hub situated in the heart of the Philippines. Lucena City serves as the specific locale for this study, focusing on the local trucking service businesses operating within the region. The goal is to explore operational challenges, identify opportunities, and assess the overall landscape of logistics management within the Lucena City trucking industry.

Population and Sampling

Lucena City, a hub for trucking services, was home to five prominent companies, including NLT Trucking Services, Phil-Nippon Kyoei Corporation, NLT Trucking Services Inc., JRS Express, and Sto Domingo Lines. These businesses served a substantial monthly customer base of 30 to 40 clients each. The research focused on these valued customers, with 150 respondents selected through purposive sampling for their crucial insights and experiences relevant to the present investigation. The selection of respondents was determined using the sample proportion method, and the Raosoft calculator was utilized for sample size calculation.

Data Gathering Procedure

In this research, a carefully designed questionnaire, informed by relevant literature, underwent rigorous validation, including expert reviews and pilot testing. The target population, Lucena City's trucking business services, was selected using a suitable sample size and method. Participants were contacted, assured of confidentiality, and requested to participate. Data collection involved systematic entry, reliability, and validity testing, and subsequent analysis using descriptive and inferential statistics to interpret relationships between variables.

Findings were reported, interpreted, and conclusions drawn, with recommendations for Lucena City's trucking business services improvement. The process adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and participant rights. The research findings were disseminated through reports or presentations, maximizing impact on relevant stakeholders.

Instruments

The research instrument employed in this study comprised a custom-designed questionnaire, featuring statements crafted based on the insights garnered from the reviewed literature. This instrument underwent a meticulous sequence of procedures, including instrument validation, pilot testing, and the assessment of reliability and validity. The instrument was structured in alignment with the research problem, with three distinct parts:

1. The initial section was dedicated to the operational efficiency of trucking business services in Lucena City.

2. The second section addressed customer satisfaction with the trucking services they had experienced.
 3. The last section was focused on operational efficiency as the foundation of effective logistic management.
- Ethical considerations were addressed by obtaining necessary approvals, ensuring participant confidentiality, and obtaining informed consent.

Process of Analysis

The study's data treatment was rigorous, starting with a self-made questionnaire undergoing expert validation and a pilot test. Using purposive sampling and the Raosoft calculator, a representative sample from Lucena City's trucking services was selected, with participants contacted for clarity and confidentiality. Data entry followed a systematic approach, and rigorous reliability and validity testing included the Pearson correlation coefficient. The analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistics, with findings presented using data visualization techniques. Throughout, ethical considerations were prioritized, ensuring informed consent and participant confidentiality. Research findings were disseminated through reports or presentations, contributing to informed decision-making and potential improvements in Lucena City's trucking business services.

Statistical Treatment

The study "Operational Efficiency in the Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City: A Foundation for Effective Logistics Management" utilized two main statistical techniques. Firstly, it employed Pearson's R correlation analysis to assess the strength and direction of relationships between different factors affecting operational efficiency and logistics management in the trucking sector of Lucena City. This analysis revealed the level of connection between key variables such as technology adoption, regulatory compliance, and overall operational effectiveness. Moreover, the research employed weighted mean analysis to gain a thorough understanding of the significance and impact of various variables on operational efficiency. By assigning appropriate weights based on their relative importance, the weighted mean approach ensured a comprehensive evaluation of the contributing factors. These statistical methods were chosen to provide correlation insights and detailed assessments, allowing for a comprehensive examination of operational dynamics in the trucking service industry in Lucena City.

Scope and Limitations

The research titled "Operational Efficiency in the Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City: A Foundation for Effective Logistics Management" focused on the operational intricacies of the local trucking industry in Lucena City, Philippines. The study comprehensively explored factors such as traffic congestion, road conditions, regulatory compliance, and technology adoption within the specified geographical area. The research aimed to provide valuable insights into current trends, challenges, and opportunities to offer practical recommendations for enhancing operational efficiency and logistics management for trucking service businesses in Lucena City. However, it is important to note that the findings were subject to temporal constraints, sample size limitations, external factors, resource constraints, and the need for cautious generalization beyond the specific locale. Despite these limitations, the study aimed to provide a valuable basis for enhancing the overall efficiency of trucking operations and logistics management in Lucena City.

RESULTS

The results below align with the research's statement of the problem.

1. Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City

The findings from various dimensions of operational efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business revealed crucial factors that significantly contributed to the industry's overall efficiency and customer satisfaction. In terms of tangibles, the well-kept facilities, with a dominant weighted mean of 3.9, underscored the pivotal role of facility maintenance and investment in enhancing the business image and operational efficiency. Reliability, marked by a consistently high weighted mean of 3.8, highlighted the importance of factors such as delivery schedules, commitment adherence, and staff training in shaping the trucking service's reliability. Assurance-related dimensions emphasized staff training, quality control, clear information, and transparent communication as highly efficient factors, collectively enhancing operational efficiency. In the realm of empathy, tailoring services to customer needs was identified as the most efficient factor, alongside other contributors like effective communication and customer-centric policies. The paramount factor in responsiveness was the swift resolution of customer inquiries, emphasizing the industry's dedication to prompt and effective responsiveness, significantly enhancing operational efficiency.

2. Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses

In assessing the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction across various dimensions. In terms of tangibles, aesthetics, integration of modern technology, and professional information presentation were highlighted as crucial elements. Regarding reliability, safety, and secure handling practices, they received notably high satisfaction, with a weighted mean of 3.77. In terms of assurance, employee training, transparent communication, and implemented policies, they all significantly contributed to exceptionally high satisfaction. The weighted means for assurance, employee training, and implemented policies were 3.86, 3.41, and 3.73, respectively. The empathy dimension reflected exceptionally high satisfaction, emphasizing the influence of personalized services, employee performance, and anticipation and response to customer needs. In terms of responsiveness, Lucena City's trucking service businesses received overwhelmingly positive ratings of "Highly Satisfied." Prompt responses, timely communication, and quick adaptation were identified as key factors, each obtaining significantly higher weighted means of 3.01, 2.85, and 3.07, respectively.

3. Relationship Between Efficiency and Customer Satisfaction in Lucena City's Trucking Services

Regarding the connection between operational efficiency and customer satisfaction in the trucking services industry of Lucena City, the Pearson correlation coefficient of .755 ($p < .001$) suggested a strong positive relationship. This indicated that an improvement in operational efficiency was generally associated with increased customer satisfaction, whereas a decrease in efficiency was connected to a decrease in satisfaction.

4. Operational Efficiency as Foundation and Sustainability of Effective Logistics Management

In terms of operational efficiency, which served as the foundation of effective logistics management, communication, coordination, customer satisfaction, and adaptability to market

changes all received unanimous "Strongly Agree" ratings. The weighted means for these factors were 3.91, 3.94, and 3.94, respectively, highlighting their crucial importance. However, continuous improvement strategies, which were categorized as "Agree" with a weighted mean of 2.68, suggested that there was room for improvement in sustaining operational efficiency and effective logistics management. The findings underscored the critical importance of specific factors in establishing a strong foundation for logistics management, despite the potential for improvement through continuous improvement strategies. According to participant responses, the following elements could serve as the foundation of effective logistics management: operational practices, technological integration, timeliness of deliveries, communication and coordination, customer satisfaction, training and skill development, adaptability to market changes, sustainability practices, and continuous improvement strategies

DISCUSSION

Operational Efficiency of Trucking Services Businesses Using SERVQUAL Dimensions

Table 1: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business in Terms of Tangibles

Operational Efficiency: Tangibles	(4) Highly Efficient	(3) Efficient	(2) Moderately Efficient	(1) Highly Inefficient	WM	QD
The state of our trucks and equipment significantly affects our service reliability and meeting customer expectations.	127	19	4		3.8	Highly Efficient
Truck and equipment condition crucially shapes how our customers perceive our service quality.	115	31	1		3.7	Highly Efficient
Well-kept facilities boost our professionalism and reliability in the eyes of our customers.	132	17	1		3.9	Highly Efficient
Modern technology investments directly impact our service's tangibility, affecting customer satisfaction.	130	20			3.9	Highly Efficient
Adequate maintenance of our tangible assets, like vehicles and facilities, instills customer confidence in our trucking services' reliability.	130	14	6		3.8	Highly Efficient

Table 1 presents a comprehensive analysis of the distribution of responses on operational efficiency in terms of tangibles within Lucena City's trucking service business. The data is arranged in descending order of Weighted Mean scores. The impact of well-maintained facilities on professionalism and reliability resulted in a weighted mean of 3.9, emphasizing its effectiveness and positive impact on the overall business image. The direct impact of investments in modern technology is closely followed, with a weighted mean of 3.9, emphasizing its significant contribution to the tangibility of services and customer satisfaction. The state of trucks and equipment, which is recognized for its significant impact on service reliability, maintained a weighted mean of 3.8. Adequate maintenance of tangible assets, such as vehicles and facilities, also received praise with a weighted mean of 3.8, instilling customer confidence in the reliability of trucking services. Lastly, the condition of the truck and equipment, which is crucial in shaping customer perceptions of service quality, was deemed "highly efficient" with a weighted mean of 3.7.

The results emphasized the significant weighted mean of 3.9 in the impact of well-maintained facilities on professionalism and reliability, highlighting the crucial role of maintaining and investing in facilities. This underscored the significance of enhancing the overall business image and operational efficiency within the trucking service industry in Lucena City.

The results emphasized the significant weighted mean of 3.9 in the Impact of Well-Kept Facilities on Professionalism and Reliability, highlighting the crucial role of maintaining and investing in facilities (Table 1). This underscored the significance of enhancing the overall business image and operational efficiency within the trucking service industry in Lucena City. This finding resonates with insights from a related study that focuses on educational facilities. The study emphasizes the importance of a well-maintained school environment for academic excellence (Texas Association of School Boards, 2023). The educational study reveals a clear link between the quality of the learning environment and student achievement. This aligns with the impact that well-maintained facilities have on professionalism and reliability in the trucking service industry. Educational leaders, such as Jeff Clemmons, emphasize the importance of conducting honest assessments and making improvements to address disparities in learning environments. This mirrors the emphasis placed on the crucial role of maintenance and investment in trucking service facilities (Texas Association of School Boards, 2023). High-performing boards and school districts recognize the positive impact of investing in facilities on various aspects, including student health, attendance, behavior, and academic performance. This reflects the broader influence on the overall business image and operational efficiency, as seen in Lucena City (Texas Association of School Boards, 2023). The benefits extend to teachers, who experience improved morale and instructional environments, mirroring the positive cycle created by well-maintained facilities in the trucking service industry. The focus on healthy facilities in education, as highlighted by Karen Shwind, parallels the emphasis on the impact of well-kept facilities on professionalism and reliability in Lucena City's trucking service industry (Texas Association of School Boards, 2023).

Table 2: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business
In terms of Reliability

Operational Efficiency: Reliability	(4) Highly Efficient	(3) Efficient	(2) Moderately Efficient	(1) Highly Inefficient	WM	QD
Consistent delivery schedules and commitment adherence shape our reliability.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Timely customer inquiry responses drive reliability in meeting expectations.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Safety and secure handling practices are paramount for service reliability.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Dependable vehicle maintenance and quality control are crucial for reliability.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Well-trained staff significantly contribute to our reliability and customer satisfaction.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient

In Table 2, the distribution of responses on operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking service business, specifically focusing on reliability, was presented. The highest weighted mean of 3.8 was consistently attributed to various aspects, including consistent delivery schedules,

commitment adherence, timely customer inquiry responses, safety practices, secure handling, dependable vehicle maintenance, quality control, and well-trained staff. This consistency in the weighted means highlighted the crucial role of these factors in influencing the reliability of the trucking service. The qualitative description classified all of these criteria as "highly efficient," emphasizing their utmost significance in contributing to the overall reliability and customer satisfaction in the trucking industry of Lucena City.

In Table 2, the distribution of responses on operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking service business, with a specific focus on reliability, was presented. The highest weighted mean of 3.8 was consistently attributed to various aspects, including consistent delivery schedules, commitment adherence, timely customer inquiry responses, safety practices, secure handling, dependable vehicle maintenance, quality control, and well-trained staff. This uniformity in the weighted means emphasized the critical role of these factors in shaping the reliability of the trucking service, categorizing them as "Highly Efficient" in the qualitative description. This concept of reliability and operational efficiency aligned with the broader understanding that operational efficiency is crucial in ensuring consistent and reliable delivery of high-quality services or products.

By minimizing waste in time, effort, and materials, organizations can improve their ability to meet customer expectations. The financial aspect, expressed through the ratio between input and output, encompasses key elements such as rapid development times, quality, and customer retention, all of which contribute to the overall reliability of the organization. Streamlining core operations, eliminating redundancies, and focusing on resource utilization, production organization, and distribution efficiency are integral steps in achieving operational efficiency. These steps directly influence the reliability of the processes. Continuous improvement strategies, such as monitoring performance, minimizing waste, and measuring indicators like automation accuracy and customer satisfaction, not only contribute to operational efficiency but also strengthen the reliability of the organization in delivering consistent and high-quality outcomes (Gillis, 2023). This holistic perspective emphasizes the interconnected nature of operational efficiency and reliability. The principles observed in Lucena City's trucking industry findings resonate with broader organizational contexts.

Table 3: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business
In terms of Assurance

Operational Efficiency: Assurance	(4) Highly Efficient	(3) Efficient	(2) Moderately Efficient	(1) Highly Inefficient	WM	QD
Staff training enhances service quality and operational efficiency.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Clear and accurate information assures customers and streamlines efficiency.	0	144	6	0	3	Highly Efficient
Quality control measures and audits positively impact assurance and efficiency.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient
Transparent customer communication ensures both assurance and efficiency.	0	144	6	0	3	Highly Efficient
Feedback and continuous improvement enhance assurance and operational efficiency.	130	14	6	0	3.8	Highly Efficient

The findings from Table 3 revealed a comprehensive assessment of the operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking service business, with a specific emphasis on assurance. Notably, staff training emerged as the most highly effective factor, achieving a weighted mean of 3.8. This underscored the pivotal role of well-trained staff in not only enhancing service quality but also contributing significantly to the overall operational efficiency within the trucking service industry. Similarly, quality control measures and audits demonstrated significant efficiency, achieving a weighted mean of 3.8. This highlighted their substantial impact on both assurance and operational efficiency. The effectiveness of clear and accurate information, as indicated by its weighted mean of 3, highlighted its importance in ensuring customer satisfaction and optimizing operational processes. Additionally, transparent customer communication and feedback initiatives for continuous improvement were also highly effective, each receiving a weighted mean score of 3.8. The qualitative description categorized all criteria as "Highly Efficient," highlighting the industry's steadfast dedication to excellence in assurance-related aspects. This, in turn, greatly enhanced the overall efficiency of trucking services in Lucena City.

Based on the results, Table 3 highlighted the significant importance of well-trained staff in improving service quality and overall operational efficiency within Lucena City's Trucking Service Business. This was evident from the highest efficiency factor, which had a weighted mean of 3.8. Additionally, quality control measures, clear and accurate information, transparent customer communication, and continuous improvement initiatives, each secured a weighted mean of 3.8, further emphasizing the industry's commitment to excellence in assurance-related dimensions. These collective findings significantly contributed to the overall operational efficiency of trucking services in Lucena City, categorizing all criteria as "highly efficient."

Operational efficiency, in terms of assurance, refers to an organization's capacity to ensure the reliability, security, and compliance of its operations with applicable regulations and standards. This involves implementing measures to proactively prevent errors, minimize risks, and maintain strict quality control standards. Best practices for enhancing operational efficiency in terms of assurance include regularly conducting audits and risk assessments, as well as identifying potential issues and areas for improvement. The implementation of robust security measures is imperative to shield against cyber threats and data breaches, while also ensuring compliance with pivotal regulations and standards such as ISO 9001 or SOC 2. Furthermore, the provision of ongoing training and education to employees plays a critical role in fostering a culture of quality and continuous improvement within the organization (Hayes, 2022). In the context of Lucena City's trucking service industry, the highlighted findings in Table 3 align with and reinforce these best practices, demonstrating the industry's commitment to maintaining high levels of operational efficiency related to assurance.

Table 4: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business
In terms of Empathy

Operational Efficiency: Empathy	(4) Highly Efficient	(3) Efficient	(2) Moderately Efficient	(1) Highly Inefficient	WM	QD
Tailoring services to customer needs enhances empathy and operational efficiency.	130	20	0	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Effective customer communication positively impacts both empathy and efficiency.	0	150	0	0	3	Highly Efficient
Customer-centric policies foster empathy and efficient issue resolution.	130	20	0	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Empowering employees enhances empathy and boosts service efficiency.	130	20	0	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
A proactive approach in responding to customer needs improves empathy and overall service efficiency.	0	150	0	0	3	Highly Efficient

Table 4 presented the distribution of responses on operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking service business, with a focus on empathy. Notably, tailoring services to customer needs emerged as the most highly efficient factor, achieving a weighted mean of 3.9. This highlighted the crucial role of customization in improving both empathy and overall operational efficiency within the trucking service industry. Similarly, effective customer communication achieved a highly efficient weighted mean of 3, highlighting its positive impact on both empathy and efficiency. Customer-centric policies and empowering employees also contributed significantly to empathy and service efficiency, both of which resulted in a highly efficient weighted mean of 3.9. A proactive approach in responding to customer needs, with a weighted mean of 3, demonstrated its effectiveness in enhancing empathy and overall service efficiency. The qualitative description categorized all criteria as "Highly Efficient," emphasizing the industry's dedication to providing excellent and empathetic customer service, which significantly contributed to the overall efficiency of trucking services in Lucena City.

Table 4 revealed that, in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business, tailoring services to customer needs was the most highly efficient factor (weighted mean of 3.9). This emphasized the crucial role of customization in enhancing both empathy and overall operational efficiency within the industry. Effective customer communication, customer-centric policies, empowering employees, and a proactive approach to responding to customer needs also significantly contributed to empathy and service efficiency. Each of these factors secured a highly efficient weighted mean of 3.9. These results underscored the industry's commitment to providing excellent and empathetic customer service, which significantly contributed to the overall efficiency of trucking services in Lucena City.

Operational efficiency, in terms of empathy, encompasses an organization's ability to balance efficiency and productivity while fostering emotional connections and understanding among team members and customers. While empathy may be perceived as a potential impediment to efficiency, it is instrumental in cultivating improved communication, collaboration, innovation, and creativity within teams. Moreover, empathy contributes to enhanced customer service and the development of products and services that align more closely with customer needs. Striking the right balance between empathy and productivity poses a challenge, especially in fast-paced and

high-pressure work environments. Best practices for achieving operational efficiency in terms of empathy involve providing ongoing training and education to employees to cultivate a culture of empathy and emotional intelligence. This includes paying attention to employee emotions and offering support when needed. Integrating empathy-focused services and tools, such as Empathy, into existing systems is recommended to enhance the overall customer experience (Pluralsight, 2023). In Lucena City's trucking service industry, the highlighted findings in Table 4 align with best practices, demonstrating the industry's dedication to operational efficiency based on empathy and customer-centric practices.

Table 5: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business
In terms of Responsiveness

Operational Efficiency: Responsiveness	(4) Highly Efficient	(3) Efficient	(2) Moderately Efficient	(1) Highly Inefficient	WM	QD
Quick resolution of customer inquiries enhances efficiency in Lucena City's trucking, showing responsiveness.	130	20	0	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Timely communication of service changes contributes to efficiency in Lucena City's trucking, reflecting responsiveness.	126	20	4	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Swift adaptation to changing customer needs improves operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking.	125	20	5	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Efficient handling of challenges demonstrates high responsiveness in Lucena City's trucking.	130	20	0	0	3.9	Highly Efficient
Prompt adjustment to demand variations positively influences Lucena City's trucking efficiency, indicating responsiveness.	110	25	5	0	3.9	Highly Efficient

Table 5 presented the Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business, with a specific focus on Responsiveness. Notably, the quick resolution of customer inquiries stood out as the most highly efficient factor. However, the weighted mean was not provided in the data. Following closely, timely communication of service changes, swift adaptation to changing customer needs, efficient handling of challenges, and prompt adjustment to demand variations all contributed to achieving a highly efficient weighted mean of 3.9. These findings underscored the industry's commitment to quick and adaptive responsiveness, enhancing overall operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking services. The qualitative description categorized all criteria as "Highly Efficient," emphasizing the industry's commitment to prompt and effective responsiveness, which was crucial in meeting the dynamic demands of the trucking service business in Lucena City.

The results from Table 5 highlighted that the swift resolution of customer inquiries stood out as the most efficient factor in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business. This underscored the industry's commitment to prompt and effective responsiveness, which contributed significantly to improving overall operational efficiency.

Operational efficiency, in terms of responsiveness, refers to an organization's ability to quickly and effectively adapt to changes in the market, customer needs, and internal processes. This involves implementing measures to enhance agility, flexibility, and adaptability, such as reducing lead times, optimizing processes, and embracing automation and digital transformation initiatives. Enhancing operational efficiency and responsiveness is crucial for organizations aiming to remain competitive and meet customer demands within a dynamic and rapidly changing business environment. Best practices for achieving operational efficiency in responsiveness encompass the implementation of agile methodologies to enhance project

management and collaboration, utilizing data analytics and business intelligence tools for insights into customer behavior and market trends, and making strategic investments in technology and automation to streamline processes and reduce lead times (MacGowan, 2022). Satisfaction Level of Customers on the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City

Table 6: Distribution of Responses on the Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City Regarding Tangibles

Operational Efficiency: Tangibles	(4) Highly Satisfied	(3) Satisfied	(2) Moderately Satisfied	(1) Not Satisfied	WM	QD
Truck and facility aesthetics boost my satisfaction.	88	61	1	0	3.58	Highly Satisfied
Modern technology enhances the tangible aspects.	105	35	10	0	3.63	Highly Satisfied
Professional presentation of information adds to overall satisfaction.	105	37	8	0	3.65	Highly Satisfied
Clean and organized facilities contribute to service quality satisfaction.	51	89	9	0	3.26	Satisfied
Staff appearance positively influences my satisfaction.	0	149	1	0	2.99	Satisfied

Table 6 presented the distribution of responses on the level of satisfaction with the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, with a specific focus on tangibles. Notably, respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction with the aesthetics of the trucks and facilities, attributing a weighted mean of 3.58 and categorizing it as "Highly Satisfied." Similarly, the integration of modern technology to enhance tangible aspects and the professional presentation of information both received a weighted mean of 3.63 and 3.65, respectively, categorizing them as "highly satisfied." Clean and organized facilities contributed to customer satisfaction with service quality, although at a slightly lower level. The weighted mean for this aspect was 3.26, which qualified as "Satisfied." On the other hand, staff appearance received a weighted mean of 2.99, categorizing it as "Satisfied."

Based on the results, Table 6 indicated that respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction, categorizing it as 'Highly Satisfied,' with the tangible aspects of trucking service businesses in Lucena City. This included aesthetics, modern technology integration, and professional presentation of information.

The synthesis of research findings clarifies the significant influence of service quality dimensions, particularly tangibles, on customer satisfaction in the logistics and transportation industry. Notable scholarly inquiries, such as the investigation into port logistics service quality and the comprehensive analysis of overall logistics service quality, consistently highlight the significant impact of tangible factors on the development of customer satisfaction. Furthermore, scholarly discourse emphasizes the importance of providing exceptional customer service within the logistics sector to cultivate satisfied customers, fostering long-lasting and mutually beneficial partnerships that are essential for supply chain success (Le, D. N., Nguyen, H. T., & Truong, P. H., 2020).

Despite lack absence clear definition of context shaping customer satisfaction in the trucking industry, the combined evidence highlights the crucial role of tangible factors as a key dimension of service quality that significantly influences customer satisfaction in the wider field landscape of logistics and transportation services. In the trucking service industry of Lucena City, the highlighted findings in Table 6 support these scholarly perspectives, which emphasize the importance of tangible factors in improving customer satisfaction and fostering long-term relationships within the logistics and transportation sector.

Table 7: Distribution of Responses on the Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City Regarding Reliability

Operational Efficiency: Reliability	(4) Highly Satisfied	(3) Satisfied	(2) Moderately Satisfied	(1) Not Satisfied	WM	QD
Consistent delivery schedules and commitment adherence shape our reliability.	77	32	41	0	3.24	Highly Satisfied
Timely customer inquiry responses drive reliability in meeting expectations.	0	150	0	0	3.00	Highly Satisfied
Safety and secure handling practices are paramount for service reliability.	115	35	0	0	3.77	Highly Satisfied
Dependable vehicle maintenance and quality control are crucial for reliability.	3	118	29	0	2.83	Satisfied
Well-trained staff significantly contribute to our reliability and customer satisfaction.	130	20	0	0	3.87	Satisfied

Table 7 illustrated the distribution of responses regarding the level of satisfaction with the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, with a specific focus on the dimension of reliability. The respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction, categorizing it as "Highly Satisfied," with several key factors. Notably, consistent delivery schedules and adherence to commitments were considered highly satisfactory, with a weighted mean of 3.24. Equally noteworthy was the emphasis on safety and secure handling practices, with a significantly higher weighted mean of 3.77. This indicated a prevalent sentiment of high satisfaction. Timely customer inquiry responses also contributed to a high level of satisfaction, with a weighted mean of 3.00. However, vehicle maintenance and quality control, although considered satisfactory, had a lower weighted mean of 2.83. The qualitative description affirmed that the respondents generally perceived reliability positively. They categorized both consistent delivery schedules and safety practices as "Highly Satisfied," while vehicle maintenance and quality control, though satisfactory, were labeled as "Satisfied."

Table 7 indicated that respondents overwhelmingly expressed high satisfaction with safety and secure handling practices in Lucena City's trucking service businesses. This was evidenced by the significantly higher weighted mean of 3.77.

According to Lin et al. (2023), the research findings underscore the paramount importance of reliability as a key determinant of customer satisfaction in logistics and transportation services. A study focusing on the quality of logistics services identified reliability as a crucial factor that significantly contributes to overall customer satisfaction. Likewise, an examination of public transport indicated that the reliability of services had a significant impact on user satisfaction. The broader importance of customer service in logistics is emphasized in an article that highlights

the role of reliable and resilient logistics management systems in enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering enduring customer loyalty. Taken together, these results collectively indicate that reliability is a critical dimension of service quality that significantly impacts customer satisfaction in the field of logistics and transportation services. In Lucena City's trucking service industry, the findings highlighted in Table 7 align with scholarly perspectives, emphasizing the crucial role of safety and secure handling practices in contributing to overall customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 8: Distribution of Responses on the Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City Regarding Assurance

Operational Efficiency: Assurance	(4) Highly Satisfied	(3) Satisfied	(2) Moderately Satisfied	(1) Not Satisfied	WM	QD
Transparent communication builds trust, positively impacting my satisfaction.	79	54	17	0	3.41	Highly Satisfied
Employee training contributes to assurance, influencing satisfaction.	129	21	0	0	3.86	Highly Satisfied
Implemented policies instill confidence in the service's reliability, contributing to my satisfaction.	115	29	6	0	3.73	Highly Satisfied
Accurate information about services and pricing impacts my satisfaction.	106	31	13	0	3.62	Satisfied
Continuous improvement initiatives positively influence my overall assurance, influencing satisfaction.	109	37	4	0	3.7	Satisfied

Table 8 illustrated the distribution of responses regarding the level of satisfaction with the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, specifically in terms of assurance. Respondents overwhelmingly expressed high satisfaction, categorizing it as "Highly Satisfied," with employee training, transparent communication that fostered trust and implemented policies that instilled confidence in the service's reliability. These factors obtained significantly higher weighted means of 3.86, 3.41, and 3.73, respectively, underscoring their substantial influence on overall satisfaction. Also, respondents expressed satisfaction, categorizing it as "Satisfied," with accurate information about services and pricing, which achieved a weighted mean of 3.62. Continuous improvement initiatives, while still positively influencing overall assurance, achieved a slightly lower satisfaction level, with a weighted mean of 3.7.

Based on the findings, Table 8 indicated that respondents expressed exceptionally high satisfaction, categorizing as 'Highly Satisfied,' with employee training, transparent communication fostering trust, and implemented policies instilling confidence in the service's reliability. This was reflected by their significantly higher weighted means of 3.86, 3.41, and 3.73, respectively, emphasizing their paramount influence on overall satisfaction in Lucena City's trucking service businesses.

A study on customer satisfaction with the quality of logistics services specifically highlights the impact of the assurance factor on overall satisfaction. Moreover, an article underscores the importance of customer service in logistics and transportation, emphasizing its potential to yield long-term cost savings, on-time delivery, customer satisfaction, and the generation of happy customers (Lin et al., 2023). Furthermore, the provision of reliable and resilient logistics

management systems is identified as a key element in enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering customer loyalty (Lin et al., 2023).

In the trucking service industry of Lucena City, the findings from Table 8 are consistent with these academic viewpoints, demonstrating that factors related to assurance, such as employee training, transparent communication, and reliable policies, make a substantial contribution to the overall satisfaction of customers. The highlighted findings support the existing literature that emphasizes the significance of assurance in logistics services and its positive influence on long-term customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 9: Distribution of Responses on the Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City Regarding Empathy

Operational Efficiency: Empathy	(4) Highly Satisfied	(3) Satisfied	(2) Moderately Satisfied	(1) Not Satisfied	WM	QD
Customized services boost my satisfaction.	124	19	7	0	3.78	Highly Satisfied
Employees exceeding expectations significantly enhance my satisfaction.	116	33	1	0	3.77	Highly Satisfied
Anticipation and response to customer needs positively influence my satisfaction	123	19	0	8	3.71	Highly Satisfied
Proactive approaches to customer need significantly improve my satisfaction with the service.	110	36	4	0	3.71	Satisfied
Empowering employees to provide personalized assistance contributes to my satisfaction.	104	20	0	26	3.35	Satisfied

Table 9 revealed that respondents expressed exceptionally high satisfaction, categorizing it as "Highly Satisfied," with the empathetic aspects of trucking service businesses in Lucena City. Customized services emerged as the most influential factor, garnering a highly satisfied weighted mean of 3.78. This indicated a strong positive impact on overall satisfaction. Additionally, employees who exceeded expectations and anticipated and responded to customer needs significantly contributed to customer satisfaction, with weighted means of 3.77 and 3.71, respectively. Proactive approaches to customer needs were also identified as a satisfactory factor, achieving a weighted mean of 3.71. While the empowerment of employees to provide personalized assistance was considered satisfactory, with a weighted mean of 3.35, it was noteworthy that it held a lower position compared to other factors in the empathetic dimension.

Based on the findings, Table 9 indicated that respondents expressed exceptionally high satisfaction with the empathetic aspects of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, particularly emphasizing the influence of customized services, employees exceeding expectations, and anticipation and response to customer needs as crucial factors in shaping overall satisfaction.

According to Mathis (2021), incorporating empathy into customer service practices can result in lasting transportation savings, punctual deliveries, and the development of content and satisfied customers. Another source underscores the importance of empathy in customer experience, emphasizing that organizations displaying understanding and empathy towards their customers can foster a stronger emotional connection with the brand, consequently enhancing customer satisfaction and cultivating loyalty. In this context, the research findings in Lucena City's trucking

service industry substantiate these assertions, highlighting the substantial impact of empathetic practices on customer satisfaction and loyalty within the logistics and transportation domain.

Table 10: Distribution of Responses on the Level of Satisfaction with the Operational Efficiency of Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City Regarding Responsiveness

Operational Efficiency: Responsiveness	(4) Highly Satisfied	(3) Satisfied	(2) Moderately Satisfied	(1) Not Satisfied	WM	QD
Prompt responses to inquiries positively affect my satisfaction...	14	124	12	0	3.01	Highly Satisfied
Timely communication of delivery schedule changes enhances my satisfaction	0	127	23	0	2.85	Highly Satisfied
Quick adaptation to changing customer needs positively impacts my satisfaction.	10	140	0	0	3.07	Highly Satisfied
Easily accessible communication channels contribute to my satisfaction	6	144	0	0	3.04	Satisfied
Efficient resolution of issues impacts my satisfaction.	6	144	0	0	3.04	Satisfied

Table 10 revealed that respondents expressed a high level of satisfaction, categorizing it as 'Highly Satisfied,' with the responsiveness of trucking service businesses in Lucena City. Specifically, prompt responses to inquiries, timely communication of delivery schedule changes, and quick adaptation to changing customer needs were identified as highly influential factors, indicated by their significantly higher weighted means of 3.01, 2.85, and 3.07, respectively. The findings emphasized the paramount importance of these responsive practices in shaping positive customer experiences. Additionally, easily accessible communication channels and efficient issue resolution contributed to overall satisfaction, achieving a satisfactory weighted mean of 3.04.

Based on Table 10, respondents overwhelmingly expressed 'Highly Satisfied' ratings for the responsiveness of Lucena City's trucking service businesses, with prompt responses to inquiries, timely communication of delivery schedule changes, and quick adaptation to changing customer needs identified as highly influential factors, each obtaining significantly higher weighted means of 3.01, 2.85, and 3.07, respectively.

According to Lin (2023), the influence of responsiveness, a key service quality dimension, significantly shapes customer satisfaction in logistics and transportation services. A comprehensive study examining the impact of logistics service quality on customer satisfaction highlights responsiveness as a pivotal dimension crucial for overall satisfaction. Additionally, an article emphasizes the strategic importance of direct communication in the transportation and logistics sector, underscoring the necessity of responsiveness to meet customer needs and expectations. While specific insights on customer satisfaction within the trucking business are lacking, the amalgamated search results strongly suggest that responsiveness plays a fundamental role as a service quality dimension influencing customer satisfaction across the broader spectrum of logistics and transportation services.

In Lucena City's trucking service industry, the results from Table 10 align with these scholarly perspectives, indicating that responsiveness-related factors significantly contribute to overall customer satisfaction. The findings reinforce the broader literature's emphasis on the importance

of responsiveness in logistics services and its positive impact on customer satisfaction in the dynamic and evolving landscape of the transportation sector.

Relationship Between Operational Efficiency (SERVQUAL Dimensions) And Customer Satisfaction

Table 11: Distribution of Responses on the Relationship Between Efficiency and Customer Satisfaction Regarding Trucking Services Businesses in Lucena City

		Operational Efficiency	Customer Satisfaction
Operational Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	1	.755**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Customer Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.755**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 11 illustrated the correlation between operational efficiency and customer satisfaction within the trucking services industry in Lucena City. The Pearson correlation coefficient for operational efficiency and customer satisfaction was determined to be .755 ($p < .001$), signifying a strong positive correlation. This suggested that an increase in operational efficiency was associated with a corresponding increase in customer satisfaction, and conversely, a decline in efficiency was linked to a decrease in satisfaction.

The TRUX Team (2023) highlighted the profound correlation between efficient operations and heightened customer satisfaction across diverse industries, particularly in the trucking services sector. The attainment of real-time visibility for vehicles and cargo emerges as a pivotal factor in augmenting both operational efficiency and customer contentment. This visibility provides businesses with the capability to monitor the precise location and status of their assets, thereby fostering a seamless operational process.

A critical contributor to this correlation is efficient dispatching. The positive outcomes of effective dispatching include timely deliveries, optimal resource utilization, and reduced operational costs, ultimately resulting in an elevated level of customer satisfaction. Operational process optimization, encompassing a comprehensive assessment of workflows, scheduling, dispatching, and data-driven decision-making, proved to be instrumental in fortifying operational efficiency. This optimization not only curtailed fuel consumption but also enhanced the quality of customer service.

The importance of effective logistics management cannot be overstated within this context. The incorporation of automation, real-time data utilization, and streamlined processes serves to optimize supply chain and warehouse management. This optimization, in a cascading effect, leads to cost-effective and efficient logistics operations, thereby positively influencing customer satisfaction.

The translation of increased operational efficiency within trucking companies directly manifests in improved customer satisfaction. The ability to meet project schedules, minimize delays, and

reduce costs emerges as a direct outcome of enhanced operational efficiency. This collective evidence underscores the inherent interdependence of efficient operations and customer satisfaction within the trucking services industry.

Operational Efficiency as The Foundation of Effective Logistics Management

Table 12: Distribution of Responses on Operational Efficiency as Foundation of Effective Logistics Management

Operational Efficiency: Foundation of Effective Logistic Management	(4) Strongly Agree	(3) Agree	(2) Disagree	(1) Strongly Disagree	WM	QD
Operational Practices: (Lucena City's trucking prioritizes efficient practices for logistics management.)	6	142	1	1	3.02	Agree
Technological Integration: (Technology is integrated to enhance logistics efficiency in Lucena City's trucking services.)	8	140	2	0	3.04	Agree
Resource Allocation: (Lucena City's trucking services use effective strategies for logistics resource allocation.)	5	144	1	0	3.03	Agree
Timeliness of Deliveries: (Lucena City's trucking services' operational efficiency impacts timely deliveries and contributes to effective logistics management.)	4	143	3	0	3.01	Agree
Communication and Coordination: (Effective communication and coordination in Lucena City's trucking services contribute to logistics management.)	136	14	0	0	3.91	Strongly Agree
Customer Satisfaction: (Operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking services influences customer satisfaction and contributes to effective logistics management.)	141	9	0	0	3.94	Strongly Agree
Training and Skill Development: (Lucena City's trucking services initiate training for operational efficiency and logistics management support.)	11	139	0	0	3.07	Agree
Adaptability to Market Changes: (Lucena City's trucking services adapt to market changes, contributing to effective logistics management.)	141	9	0	0	3.94	Strongly Agree
Sustainability Practices: (Lucena City's trucking services embrace sustainable practices, contributing to an effective logistics management foundation.)	11	130	9	0	3.01	Agree
Continuous Improvement Strategies: (Lucena City's trucking services implement continuous improvement strategies for enhanced operational efficiency and sustained effective logistics management.)	51	0	99	0	2.68	Agree

Table 12 illustrated the distribution of responses regarding the perception of operational efficiency as the foundation of effective logistics management in Lucena City's trucking services. The results revealed a strong consensus among respondents, with the qualitative description categorized as "Agree" to "Strongly Agree." Notably, communication and coordination, customer satisfaction, and adaptability to market changes emerged as the highest-rated factors, all receiving a weighted mean of 3.91, 3.94, and 3.94, respectively, indicating a unanimous "Strongly Agree" response. These findings underscored the pivotal role of these aspects in shaping an effective logistics management foundation. On the other hand, continuous improvement strategies, while still receiving an "Agree" categorization with a weighted mean of 2.68, suggested room for enhancement in implementing strategies for sustained operational efficiency and effective logistics management.

According to the results depicted in Table 12, respondents exhibited a robust consensus, firmly aligning with the designation of "Strongly Agree," affirming the pivotal role played by operational efficiency in shaping the bedrock of effective logistics management within Lucena City's trucking services. This resounding agreement was underpinned by key factors, notably the resolute endorsements for effective communication and coordination, customer satisfaction, adaptability to market changes, and commitment to sustainability practices. These aspects were collectively recognized as indispensable components for laying the groundwork for a successful logistics management system. While the degree of agreement was somewhat diminished for continuous improvement strategies, it is noteworthy that these strategies still commanded a favorable perception among the surveyed participants.

According to Omoush (2022), operational efficiency serves as a foundational pillar in the realm of effective logistics management, exerting a pivotal influence on the enhancement of customer satisfaction. This symbiotic relationship is notably apparent in the optimization of logistics operations, where the convergence of cost reduction and heightened efficiency works synergistically to elevate overall profitability. The spectrum of effective logistics management incorporates strategic elements, including automation, real-time data utilization, and streamlined processes, creating a harmonious environment for optimizing supply chain and warehouse management. A well-orchestrated logistics framework not only assists companies in meeting customer expectations, minimizing delays, and controlling costs but also contributes to an enriched customer satisfaction paradigm. These benefits extend beyond satisfaction to encompass increased revenue generation and an improved bottom line for businesses. Consequently, strategic investments in technology, prudent partnerships with suppliers, and an unwavering commitment to continuous improvement emerge as imperative for businesses aspiring to attain operational efficiency and, thereby, enhance customer satisfaction.

Conclusions

In light of the summarized findings, this research draws the following conclusions:

1. In conclusion, the analysis of operational efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business reveals critical factors contributing to industry efficiency and customer satisfaction. Well-kept facilities highlight the importance of maintenance, reliability emphasizes factors like delivery schedules and staff training, and assurance-related dimensions contribute to overall operational efficiency. Ensuring services meet customer needs showcases empathy, while responsiveness is marked by the swift resolution of inquiries, showcasing the industry's commitment to prompt and effective customer service. These findings offer valuable insights for optimizing business practices and enhancing customer satisfaction in Lucena City's trucking service industry.
2. Regarding the satisfaction level with the operational efficiency of trucking service businesses in Lucena City, the assessment highlights elevated satisfaction across diverse dimensions. Noteworthy aspects encompass aesthetics, technology integration, and information presentation in tangible aspects. Additionally, high satisfaction is observed in reliability, assurance-related factors, empathy, and responsiveness, indicating a comprehensive positive evaluation.
3. In conclusion, the analysis of the relationship between operational efficiency and customer satisfaction in Lucena City's trucking businesses reveals a robust positive connection, supported by a Pearson correlation coefficient of .755 ($p < .001$). This implies that heightened operational efficiency correlates with increased customer satisfaction, underscoring the significance of efficiency in shaping positive customer perceptions, while a decline in efficiency is associated with reduced satisfaction levels.
4. The study concludes that communication, coordination, customer satisfaction, and adaptability to market changes are unanimously recognized as essential foundations for effective logistics management. While continuous improvement strategies are acknowledged, indicating room for enhancement, the findings emphasize the critical importance of these specific factors in establishing a robust logistics management foundation. According to participant responses, key elements include Operational Practices, Technological Integration, Timeliness of Deliveries,

Customer Satisfaction, Training and Skill Development, Adaptability to Market Changes, Sustainability Practices, and Continuous Improvement Strategies.

Recommendations

Drawing from the study's summary, findings, and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Optimize operational efficiency and customer satisfaction in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business by prioritizing facility maintenance, ensuring reliable delivery schedules, investing in staff training, and enhancing assurance-related dimensions. Emphasize customer needs in service provision and maintain swift responses to inquiries for overall business success and customer satisfaction.
2. Optimize operational efficiency in Lucena City's Trucking Service Business, consider implementing predictive maintenance systems for reliable equipment performance and minimizing disruptions. Establishing customer feedback loops ensures tailored services and improved satisfaction. Invest in sustainable practices, such as eco-friendly technologies, and integrate technology into staff training programs. Embrace agile logistics strategies, utilize customer relationship management systems, foster a continuous improvement culture, and collaborate with technology partners for overall efficiency and enhanced customer satisfaction.
3. In light of the study's findings, real-life recommendations for enhancing logistics management effectiveness include fostering transparent communication channels among team members, implementing customer-centric policies to boost satisfaction, staying agile in response to market fluctuations, and investing in advanced technologies for seamless operations. Prioritize continuous improvement initiatives to refine existing processes and ensure sustainability practices are embedded in day-to-day operations. Additionally, focus on staff training programs to enhance skills and adaptability, and integrate cutting-edge technologies to streamline operational practices.
4. Further studies could explore the impact of emerging technologies, sustainability practices, and government policies on operational efficiency in Lucena City's trucking service businesses.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As authors, we affirm our unwavering commitment to upholding ethical standards in the execution of our research, titled "Operational Efficiency in the Trucking Service Businesses in Lucena City: A Foundation for Effective Logistics Management." We have diligently obtained explicit informed consent from all respondents, emphasizing their absolute right to withdraw from the study at any point. Stringent measures have been implemented to ensure the anonymity of respondents, meticulously preserving their privacy and confidentiality throughout the research process. Our dedication to data protection aligns with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) in the Philippines. It is crucial to highlight that participants were shielded from any potential harm throughout the entire duration of the research. This study adheres comprehensively to the requirements and principles outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012, emphasizing the paramount importance of safeguarding individuals' data. For any

concerns or inquiries related to the handling of personal data in this research, please feel free to contact the authors at efigenio092169@gmail.com

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